

INTERACTIVE TEACHING METHODS

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Abstract. *One of the main elements of the lesson is explanation of a new material, which includes the questions envisaged by the curriculum for this discipline. The main requirement for the lessons of explanation of the new material is the conscious assimilation of the material. In order to achieve this and to help students to take the next step in learning a foreign language, it is necessary to carefully explain the terms and concepts. For this, the teacher must use modern innovative technologies.*

Key words: *question, assimilation, achieve, concept, topics, innovative technologies.*

ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ

Аннотация. *Одним из основных элементов урока является объяснение нового материала, включающего вопросы, предусмотренные учебным планом по данной дисциплине. Основное требование к занятиям по объяснению нового материала - сознательное усвоение материала. Чтобы добиться этого и помочь учащимся сделать следующий шаг в изучении иностранного языка, необходимо тщательно объяснять термины и понятия. Для этого педагог должен использовать современные инновационные технологии.*

Ключевые слова: *вопрос, усвоение, достижение, концепция, темы, инновационные технологии.*

This work is devoted to the introduction of new topics using effective innovative technologies in the process of teaching English. Today, the goal of ESP training is not only to read and understand professional texts, but also to develop critical thinking, the ability to express thoughts and ideas. Innovative methods contribute to better mastering such skills as writing, reading, listening and speaking.

The use of interactive technologies in teaching English opens up new possibilities. Innovative tools are simple to use, their role is great in intensifying the lesson and increasing its emotional impact on students. It is vivid, colorful, interactive. The interactive teaching method creates a motivated interest among students in the English language, contributes to more effective learning of students, contributes to the development of socio-cultural education, enriches communication experience, provides adequate behavior in the context of intercultural interaction.

Learning foreign languages no longer a pastime: it is necessity, because it results in students achieving divergent thinking, creativity and cognitive development. According to the view of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M.Mirziyoyev, we should create the necessary conditions for the youth to acquire deep knowledge and modern professions and train a highly qualified workforce, young specialists capable of taking on responsibility for the future and further development of the country¹. In addition, our President states that in the system of

¹ Mirziyoyev Sh. M. Erkin va farovon demokratik Ozbekiston davlatini birgalikda barpo etamiz. O`zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti lavozimiga kirishish tantanali marosimiga bag`ishlangan Oliy Majlis palatasining qo`shma majlisidagi nutq. – Toshkent: “O`zbekiston”. 2016

education we attach a great importance to teaching students not merely liberal arts and vocational skills, but also required learning of foreign languages².

Moreover, according to the Resolution №1875 signed by the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December,10, 2012, “About the measures on further development of foreign language teaching and learning system”³, as well as according to our president Sh. M. Mirziyoyev’s strategies the main goal of teaching English has become to encourage students to use the target language in their life and develop their communicative skills, competency and culture using different effective innovative ways of teaching English.

Stories teach us about life, about ourselves and about others. Storytelling is a unique way for students to develop an understanding, respect and appreciation for other cultures, and can promote a positive attitude to people from different lands, races and religions.

Storytelling activities are a great way to allow students to express themselves freely and creatively in an authentic and real way.

The graduation project paper is devoted to the study of “Improving speaking ability through Storytelling”. For the purpose of radical improvement of the system of higher education, radical revision of the content of personnel training based on the priorities of socio-economic development of the country, creation of necessary conditions for training highly qualified specialists in accordance with international standards The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan № PD-2909 outlines the most important tasks for further improvement and comprehensive development of the higher education system⁴. Each higher education institution maintains close partnerships with the world's leading scientific institutions, introduces the educational process with advanced pedagogical technologies, curricula and teaching materials based on international educational standards. attraction of highly qualified teachers and scholars from foreign partner educational institutions on the basis of introduction of master classes in educational and pedagogical activity, training courses on the basis of the system of higher education institutions of the Republic and other relevant issues such as organizing internships, retraining and professional development for faculty and staff.

Today is the whole world teaching foreign languages, especially English has become an essential part of education in all its branches. We can even find two main types of English language teaching methodology like teaching English using traditional and modern methodology. But at the latest period in the whole world teachers tend to use modern methodology all the time. This becomes clear when we look at the results achieved using these two methods. As results show today modern methodology allows learns to communicate the real language rather than the traditional method. Taking into consideration this factor the government of our country is doing a lot in order to develop foreign language teaching in Uzbekistan using modern methodology. As it is mentioned in this decree, it is important to teach foreign languages using communicative methods, which enables teachers to encourage their students to become creative learners. In this work we decided to analyze the peculiarities of both traditional and modern methodology of

² Jalolov J., Makhkamova G., Ashurov Sh. English Language Teaching Methodology, Tashkent-2015

³ Karimov I.A. Presidential Decree №1875, About the measures on further development of foreign language teaching and learning system, 2012

⁴ Decree on April 30,2017 of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev on “Measures for the Further Development of Higher Education”

teaching English. Clearly, one of the aims of any methodology in foreign language teaching is to improve the foreign language ability of the student. However, traditional methodology is based largely on a reduction on the integrated process of using a foreign language into subsets of discrete skills and areas of knowledge in isolation. Following on from this, traditional methodologies are strongly associated with the teaching of language which is used in a certain field related to the students' life or work. As stated in the book "Teaching English as a foreign language", "the recognition that many students of English need the language for specific instrumental purposes has led to the teaching of ESP-English for Special or teaching output created: they uniform the reader about "the proliferation of courses and materials being designed to teach English for science, medicine, agriculture, engineering, tourism and like "⁵, which actually meant that the content of the course was limited to the specific vocabulary and grammar of the chosen field. Unlike traditional methodology, modern mythology is much more student-centered. According to Jim Scrivener, the teacher's main role is to "help learning to happen" which includes "involving" students in what is going on "by enabling them to work at their own speed, by not giving long explanations, by encouraging them to participate talk, interact, do things, etc⁶.

The reason of choosing this theme is that we are interested in methods of teaching English focusing on the development of language learning skills. Teaching should be student-centered, motivation springs from within, it can be sparked, but not imposed from without, language learning and teaching are successful when they meet student's needs in particular circumstance, the acquired language skills must serve the students in everyday life. Language teaching and language learning are successful if they look like a cooperation process when one's feelings, values and aspirations are revealed either at a very deep level or in surface activities such as games, simulations, dramatizations, etc. Students should acquire knowledge of the language actively through use as experience is constantly transformed by deeds. Control of language includes the ability to understand messages and implicate them in the context. Development of language control is impossible without creativity when students experience the use of the new language as an important social skill.⁷ Various activities are related to literary, historical, philosophical, sociological or other content being studied in the language. New medium present additional opportunities for students to view and hear themselves as they attempt to use the language in authentic ways. As for testing, it shouldn't be punitive, it should be a learning experience that is part of the on going course, involving students in working out interesting problems, being motivational and a means of growth for students. Interactive methods make it possible entrance another culture, developing are tolerance for difference without confusion of the own sense of identity. The use of interactive methods also implies taking the language and its learning out of the classroom as the world opens up through travel, technology and shared interests. Second language learning is a developmental process. Learners use existing knowledge to make the

⁵ Celce-Murcia, M. (Ed.). (2001). Teaching English as a second or foreign language. Boston: Heinle & Heinle.

⁶ Pat Grogan. English pronunciation. Longman-London, 2000, 57 pages.

⁷ Кадирова Ф. Х. New approaches and modern methods of teaching foreign language pronunciation // Молодой ученый. — 2016. — №25. — С. 542-544. — URL <https://moluch.ru/archive/129/35514/>.

incoming information comprehensible and they must actively use the new information, while introduction, interactive methods teacher should take into considerations students preferred learning style and to much the teaching style to achieve optimal learning in the classroom.

Nowadays our country is looking like a big construction field, where new industrial enterprises, buildings of educational centers, changing and improving the outlook of towns and promote increase of the social economic and cultural level of life of the Uzbek people.

Uzbekistan is directly and purposefully going forward on its own way of development that is thoroughly and basically thought over by the President of the Republic. Worldwide reforms in multinational state during the years of independence are being effected and will be effected for the noble goal itself- peace, prosperity and happy life.

In the given theoretical part of work it is necessary to pay attention on those basic statements in which the most essential parts of activity are reflected and generalized. That means the methodical principles underlying teaching.

Principles of teaching are understood as starting statements which determine the purposes, the contents, methods and the organization of teaching and are shown in interrelation and interconditionality. In our case principles are used to define strategy and tactics of teaching English language at all stages practically in each point of educational process.

As far as the result of teaching of students foreign language is formation their skills of using language as means of intercourse, the leading principle is the principle of a communicative orientation.

Its main function is in creation of all conditions of communications: motives, purposes and problems of intercourse. The communicative orientation defines selection and the organization of language material, its situational conditionality, communicative value both speech and training exercises, communicative formulation of educational problems, organization and structure of the lesson. This principle assumes creation of conditions for speaking and intellectual activity of students during each moment of teaching.

Proceeding from the aforesaid teacher should follow the rules:

1) Principle of communicative orientation

- Rule 1 - Selection of situations.
- Rule 2 - Recurrence and novelty.
- Rule 3 - Participation of everyone in intercourse.
- Rule 4 - Favorable conditions for intercourse.
- Rule 5 - Communicativeness of tasks.

As far as students have still insignificant experience of collective intercourse and they are taught not only to associate in English, but also to associate in general, teacher should provide the support on students' realizing the models of intercourse in native language, realizing the communicative function of this or that language unit. Realization of this principle is carried out through system of cognitive problems, solving which students "open" laws of the native language.

On the basis of this realizing there is student's acquaintance with the form and functions of corresponding units of English language.

Proceeding from this, it is possible to plan some rules - following which allows realizing this principle in teaching and educational process.

2) Principle of support on the native language:

- Rule 1. Display of generality between Russian and English languages.
- Rule 2. Formation of the common educational skills.
- Rule 3. Use of similarity and distinctions in the script.
- Rule 4. Use of similarity and distinctions in pronunciation.
- Rule 5. Uses of carry and avoidance of interference in teaching vocabulary and grammar.

It is established, that for each kind of speaking activity "set" of actions and even the lexical and grammatical registration. It has allowed to formulate methodical principle of the differentiated approach in teaching a foreign language.

Thus the differentiation is carried out as though at different levels of generalization - precise differentiation is conducted in teaching:

- oral and written speech;
- speaking and listening;
- reading aloud and reading silently;
- script and spelling.

In teaching English language process of integration is realized, it shows, first of all, that mastering of various aspects of language, its phonetics, grammar, lexicon occurs not separately as certain discrete components of language, but is also integrated. Students seize and acquire them during carrying out of speech actions which realization can demand the use of a word, word forms, a word-combination, superphrase unity and, at last, the text, caused by situations of intercourse.

Considering the given specific principle of teaching the English language it is possible to formulate rules, their observance will help the teacher to realize this principle.

3) Principle of differentiation and integration:

- Rule 1. The account of specificity of each kind of speaking activity.
- Rule 2. Use of teacher's speech and sound recording for listening.
- Rule 3. Teaching monologic speech, proceeding from features of each form.
- Rule 4. Teaching reading aloud and silently in view of features of each form.
- Rule 5. Mastering of aspects of language in speech units.
- Rule 6. Use semi-typed font in teaching writing.

In a basis of teaching any subject at institute including foreign language, there are general didactic principles. Such principles are: scientific character, availability, presentation in teaching, an individual approach in conditions of collective work and others.

Specific and general didactic principles express typical, main, essential, that should characterize teaching a foreign language at institute and, first of all at the beginning stage where bases of mastering are pawned by this subject. The understanding of action of principles of teaching and direct use of rules will allow the teacher to carry out teaching effectively.

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